

The association between life-time dietary cadmium intake from rice and chronic kidney disease

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ABSTRACT

The association between internal cadmium exposure and chronic kidney disease (CKD) has been investigated before. However, few studies have shown the association between dietary cadmium intake and CKD. In this study, we show the association between life-time dietary cadmium intake and CKD based on a follow-up study. At baseline, we collected blood and urine samples for assays of cadmium and renal effect biomarkers. A questionnaire and food survey was given to each subject to collect diet and lifestyle information for the estimation of cadmium intake. Dietary cadmium, cadmium in blood and urine were regarded as exposure markers. Life-time dietary cadmium intake was estimated based on an individual's daily cadmium intake and exposure time. At follow-up, 467 persons (163 men and 304 women) were finally included. CKD at follow-up was considered if the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m². The eGFR level in subjects in the highest quartile of total dietary cadmium intake (>9.34 g) was significantly lower than in those with a moderate or low intake ($p < 0.01$). eGFR was negatively associated with total dietary cadmium intake ($\beta = -0.42$, 95% confidence interval (CI): -0.77 to -0.07) after adjustment with confounders. Logistic regression further showed that the risk of CKD in subjects with a high total dietary cadmium intake (>2.2 g) was higher than in those with a low intake (odds ratio (OR) = 18.16, 95%CI: 1.75–188.85). A similar association was found between the baseline urinary albumin (UALB) level and CKD incidence. A predictive model based on UALB and life-time dietary cadmium intake showed an acceptable performance (the area under the curve was 0.77 (95%CI: 0.65–0.88)). Our data show that high dietary cadmium exposure was associated with CKD after controlling for renal tubular dysfunction and internal cadmium exposure.

1. Introduction

Cadmium is one of the main contaminants in soil. It can accumulate in the body via the food chain or cigarette smoking. Grains and vegetables can absorb metal from soil (Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2015). The cadmium concentration in rice is usually high in cadmium-polluted areas (Cai et al., 1995; Jin et al., 2002). Cadmium exposure is related to many health issues, such as liver and renal dysfunction, cardiovascular diseases and osteoporosis (Nordberg, 2009; Satarug et al., 2017; WHO, 2019). Cadmium-induced renal dysfunction, particularly of renal

tubules, has been widely investigated (Jarup and Akesson, 2009; Nordberg et al., 2014). Several studies have shown that cadmium exposure may be related to chronic kidney disease (CKD) (Buser et al., 2016; Gibb et al., 2019; Hwangbo et al., 2011). However, while several studies indicated a positive association between cadmium exposure and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), which is a marker of CKD (normal value > 90 mL/min/1.73 m²), others reported no association between them (Byber et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2018; Thomas et al., 2014). The conflicting results may be due to the differences in study design, exposure levels and exposure biomarkers among those studies. Most of

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them had a cross-sectional design and low exposure levels. Dietary, urinary (UCd), or blood cadmium (BCd) were adopted as exposure biomarkers. Those conditions may affect the final results. Longitudinal studies may provide stronger evidence.

BCd and UCd are usually used as exposure biomarkers. Urinary N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (UNAG) and beta-2-microglobulin are usually used as renal effect biomarkers. BCd mainly reflects the recent exposure (Jarup and Akesson, 2009) and UCd may be related to long-term exposure or the kidney burden of cadmium (Adams and Newcomb, 2014; Nordberg et al., 2014). Dietary cadmium intake is also used as a surrogate indicator of cadmium exposure (Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2015). To the best of our knowledge, there are only two longitudinal studies showing the association between dietary cadmium and CKD (Thomas et al., 2014; Shi et al., 2018). Conflicting results were reported. Thomas et al. (2014) showed that there was no strong association between dietary cadmium exposure and CKD in the general Swedish population. However, the dietary exposure levels were relatively low, at 19.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$ in men and 13.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$ in women. Shi et al. (2018) reported a significant association between dietary cadmium and CKD (Odds Ratio (OR) = 1.68–4.05). The cadmium intake level was 26.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$, which is higher than that in the Swedish population. However, the two studies did not consider the internal exposure level of cadmium in their models. Moreover, Kawata (2018) indicated that renal tubular function which is the first stage of cadmium-induced damage should be controlled during analyses. The above two longitudinal studies did not consider renal tubular function during the analysis. Further longitudinal studies are needed.

We performed a follow-up survey of the ChinaCad study in 2006. Life-time dietary cadmium intake from rice, internal exposure and renal tubular function were estimated or determined at baseline (1998) (Jin et al., 2002). In the present study, we aimed to investigate the association between life-time dietary cadmium exposure and CKD after controlling for internal cadmium exposure and renal tubular function.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study areas and population

In a baseline study, subjects who were born and lived in two cadmium-contaminated areas and one control area were included in the present study. The two areas (Jiaoweibao and Nanbaixiang) were polluted by waste-water discharged from a zinc-cadmium smelter. Subjects living in these two areas ate rice irrigated by water from a polluted river from 1961 to 1995. The cadmium concentration in rice produced in the two polluted areas was 0.48–2.4 mg/kg (Jin et al., 2002). Rice was a staple food for the local residents. From this investigation, 83.5% of the inhabitants in the two areas agreed to participate (Jin et al., 2002). Another area 40 km from the zinc-cadmium smelter was selected as a control area (the cadmium concentration in rice was 0.05 mg/kg). The subjects consumed locally produced rice through their whole lives. They had a similar lifestyle and, social and economic conditions.

The baseline study (ChinaCad study) was performed in 1998 and consisted of 302 men and 488 women (≥ 35 years old) after excluding subjects that had self-reported kidney disease and a history of diabetes. A second follow-up survey was performed in the same areas in 2006. A total of 497 subjects were followed up in 2006. We excluded subjects with missing blood or urine samples. Finally, 467 subjects (163 men and 304 women) were included in the present study (Fig. 1), which complied with the Declaration of Helsinki. There were 120 subjects in the control area, 137 subjects in a moderately polluted area and 210 subjects in heavily polluted areas. In addition, the study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of Fudan University. Formal consent was obtained from each subject.

Fig. 1. The flow chart of follow-up. A total of 497 subjects were followed up and 467 subjects were finally included in this study.

2.2. Life-time dietary cadmium intake estimation

Detailed information on total cadmium intake assay has been reported in our previous studies (Chen et al., 2018; Jin et al., 2002). Briefly, a food survey was given to each participant to collect their rice vegetable, and meat consumption per day. The preliminary investigation showed that rice was the main food in the three areas and main source of cadmium exposure. Other foods were not considered because the cadmium intake from those sources was much lower than that from rice. Smoking is another route way for cadmium exposure. Our previous data showed that the estimated cadmium uptake from smoking was 4.05 mg (Jin et al., 2002) over 25 years of exposure (20 cigarettes per day), whereas the uptake from rice ranged from 22.4 to 545.1 mg over 35 years of exposure. The life-time cadmium intake was estimated based on rice consumption (Jin et al., 2002). Rice samples were harvested from 35 households in a heavily polluted area, 50 households in a moderately polluted area and 50 households in a control area. Samples from 5 households collected from the same area were mixed together to generate a pooled sample. The cadmium concentration in the 27 pooled samples (20 samples from control and moderately polluted areas and 7 samples from a heavily polluted area) was determined using graphite-furnace atomic absorption spectrometry. An average was calculated for the estimation of life-time dietary cadmium intake. Life-time dietary cadmium intake was estimated using the following equation: cumulative intake = daily cadmium intake \times 365 \times weighting factors \times years. For subjects aged 20–59 years old, the weighting factor was 1.0; for subjects older than 60 years, the weighting factor was 0.823 (Cai et al., 1998).

2.3. Cadmium and renal function biomarkers determination

The methods for baseline cadmium and renal function biomarker determination, and validation have been reported in previous studies (Chen et al., 2018; Jin et al., 2004; Liang et al., 2012). Briefly, 5.0 mL of venous whole blood was collected from the elbow vein. A total of 10.0 mL clean catch midstream urine was collected and separately stored in metal-free tubes. Cadmium in blood (BCd) and urine (UCd) was determined using graphite-furnace atomic absorption spectrometry. Urinary albumin (UALB) was determined by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) and urinary N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase

(UNAG) was determined based on Tucker's description (Tucker et al., 1975). Serum creatinine was determined using the Jaffe kinetic method. Estimated glomerular filtration (eGFR) was calculated using the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{eGFR} &= 141 \times (\text{Scr}/\kappa, 1)^{\alpha} \times 0.993^{\text{Age}} \times 1.018(\text{iffemale}) \\ &\times 1.159(\text{ifblack}), \text{ifScr}/\kappa \\ &< 1.0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{eGFR} &= 141 \times (\text{Scr}/\kappa, 1)^{-1.209} \times 0.993^{\text{Age}} \times 1.018(\text{iffemale}) \\ &\times 1.159(\text{ifblack}), \text{ifScr}/\kappa \\ &> 1.0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where Scr is serum creatinine, κ is 0.7 for females and 0.9 for males; α is -0.329 for females and -0.411 for males. If $\text{eGFR} < 60 \text{ mL/min/} 1.73 \text{ m}^2$, chronic kidney disease is considered.

2.4. Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using commercial statistical software (SPSS16.0 or R version 3.6.2). Age, body mass index (BMI) and eGFR are shown as means with standard deviations. BCd, UCd, UNAG and UALB are shown as medians (interquartile ranges (IQRs)). Life-time dietary cadmium intake was divided into four groups according to IQR or median to show its association with eGFR or CKD. Statistical differences between the two groups were analyzed using the Mann-Whitney *U*-test or two-tailed *t*-tests. A one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's test was used to compare the eGFR levels at different quartiles of total dietary cadmium intake. A spearman correlation analysis was used to show the association between life-time dietary cadmium intake and exposure biomarkers and effect biomarkers. Multiple linear regression analysis and logistic regression analysis were performed to show the association between CKD and the baseline variables. Collinearity was evaluated by a multiple linear regression analysis. In a multivariable regression analysis, three models were analyzed after controlling for confounders or modifiers. Analysis A: Model 1 included age, sex, dietary cadmium intake, UALB and UNAG. Model 2 was additionally adjusted with BMI, hypertension, drinking and smoking habits. Model 3 was further adjusted with follow-up BCd, UCd, UALB and UANG. Analysis B further considered the effects of internal cadmium level (BCd and UCd). A receiver operating curve (ROC) analysis was used to show the performance of the baseline variables in predicting the incidence of CKD. Statistical difference was taken as $p < 0.05$.

Table 1
Baseline characteristics of study population.

	Total population (n = 467)	Life-time dietary cadmium intake (g)		p	Control area n = 120	Polluted areas n = 347	p
		< 2.2 (n = 228)	≥ 2.2 (n = 239)				
Age (years)	51.2 ± 11.0	51.2 ± 11.4	51.1 ± 10.6	> 0.05	56.71 ± 12.01	49.23 ± 9.91	< 0.01
Sex (male/female)	163/304	74/154	89/150	> 0.05	40/80	123/224	> 0.05
BMI (kg/m ²)	22.9 ± 3.10	22.8 ± 3.04	23.09 ± 3.2	> 0.05	22.85 ± 3.15	22.95 ± 3.09	> 0.05
Smoking (yes)	76	42 (18.4%)	34 (14.2%)	> 0.05	26 (21.67%)	50 (14.41%)	> 0.05
Drinking (yes)	128	56 (24.6%)	62 (25.9%)	> 0.05	39 (32.5%)	89 (25.65%)	> 0.05
BCd (µg/L)	4.75 (2.13–9.35)	2.25 (1.13–4.23)	8.63 (4.75–13.63)	< 0.01	1.38 (0.75–2.13)	6.88 (4.00–11.54)	< 0.01
UCd (µg/g cr)	5.38 (2.76–11.24)	3.03 (1.55–4.74)	10.48 (6.01–16.76)	< 0.01	2.29 (1.19–3.63)	7.68 (4.19–13.86)	< 0.01
UALB (mg/g cr)	4.40 (2.10–10.10)	3.40 (1.70–8.10)	5.30 (2.50–12.20)	< 0.01	2.60 (1.50–6.35)	5.30 (2.40–11.50)	< 0.01
UNAG (U/ g cr)	5.21 (2.18–11.27)	3.13 (1.11–7.90)	7.66 (3.85–13.90)	< 0.01	2.26 (0.94–4.47)	7.00 (3.26–12.83)	< 0.01
Life-time dietary cadmium intake (g)	2.26 (0.73–9.34)	0.71 (0.46–1.67)	9.34 (7.27–11.09)	< 0.01	0.47 (0.35–0.55)	7.54 (2.08–10.38)	< 0.01
Number of CKD	15	3	12	< 0.01	1	14	> 0.05

BMI: body index mass; BCd: cadmium in blood; UCd: urinary cadmium; cr: creatinine; UNAG: urinary N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase; UALB: urinary albumin. Data was shown as mean ± standard deviation, number (percentage) or median (IQR).

3. Results

3.1. Baseline characteristics of study population

The baseline characteristics of the study population by total dietary cadmium exposure are listed in Table 1. The population was divided into two group by the median of life-time dietary cadmium intake (2.2 g). The baseline BCd, UCd, UALB and UNAG levels were higher in subjects in the high cadmium intake groups than in those in the low intake one ($p < 0.01$). No significant differences were found in the terms of age, body mass index, gender distribution, drinking and smoking habits.

We also compared the differences in the baseline characteristics of the study population from two polluted area and one control area. The baseline BCd, UCd, life-time cadmium intake, UALB and UNAG levels were higher in subjects living in the cadmium-polluted area than in those living in the control area ($p < 0.01$).

3.2. Correlation analysis

Life-time dietary cadmium intake was positively associated with renal effect biomarkers ($p < 0.01$), BCd and UCd ($p < 0.001$) (Fig. 2). Life-time dietary cadmium intake was obviously associated with age ($p < 0.01$). Fig. 3 further shows that the eGFR level in subjects in the highest quartile of life-time dietary cadmium intake was significantly lower compared to those with a moderate or low intake ($p < 0.01$).

3.3. Multiple linear regression analysis

Subsequently, the association between eGFR and baseline life-time dietary cadmium intake was assayed by using multiple linear regression analysis (Table 2). All three models indicated that eGFR was negatively associated with life-time dietary cadmium intake at baseline in the total population. β was -0.42 (95%CI: -0.75 to -0.10) after adjusting for confounders. If the baseline BCd and UCd were both included in the model, β was -0.42 (95%CI: -0.77 to -0.07) after adjusting for confounders. Similar results were also observed between the baseline UALB and eGFR [$\beta = -0.24$ (95%CI: -0.37 to -0.11) and $\beta = -0.28$ (95%CI: -0.41 to -0.15)]. A collinearity analysis showed that the condition index was 2.8–4 among baseline BCd, baseline UCd and life-time dietary cadmium intake.

3.4. Logistic analysis

We further confirmed an association between the incidence of CKD, baseline UALB and life-time dietary cadmium intake by logistic analysis (Table 3). All the models showed that the risk of CKD in subjects with a high life-time dietary cadmium intake was higher compared to those with a low intake (OR = 3.95, 95%CI: 1.18–13.16; OR = 6.22, 95%CI:

Fig. 2. The spearman correlation between exposure biomarkers and renal effect biomarkers. BMI: body mass index; BCd: cadmium in blood; UCd: urinary cadmium; UNAG: urinary N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase; UALB: urinary albumin; eGFR: estimated glomerular filtration rate. eGFR was obtained at follow-up. Total. intake: life-time dietary cadmium intake. Correlation coefficient > 0.11 or < -0.11, $p < 0.05$.

1.27–30.47; OR = 9.46, 95%CI: 1.61–55.53). Similar results were also observed if the baseline UCd (OR = 8.07, 95%CI: 1.69–37.86; OR = 31.45, 95%CI: 2.87–345.05; OR = 56.52, 95%CI: 3.51–608.78) or both BCd and UCd (OR = 5.85, 95%CI: 1.18–28.93; OR = 18.17, 95%CI: 1.81–182.19; OR = 18.16, 95%CI: 1.75–188.85) were included in the models. Similar associations were also observed between the follow-up CKD and the baseline UALB after controlling for possible confounders (OR = 1.06, 95%CI: 1.02–1.11; OR = 1.09, 95%CI: 1.03–1.16). Based on the UALB and life-time dietary cadmium intake, a regression model was developed. ROC analysis showed that the area under the curve was 0.77 (95%CI: 0.65–0.88).

4. Discussion

The association between cadmium exposure and clinically significant renal effects has been previously reported. In a systematic review, Byber et al. (2016) found no consistent evidence for Cd exposure as a cause of CKD. A recent study in China demonstrated that dietary cadmium is related to the CKD incidence based on data obtained from the China Health and Nutrition Survey (Shi et al., 2018). In the present longitudinal study, we further show that life-time dietary cadmium exposure is associated with the incidence of CKD. The model based on UALB and life-time dietary cadmium intake showed an acceptable predictive performance.

Cadmium exposure is associated with renal tubular dysfunction, which presents as elevated urinary low- molecular- weight proteins (Akesson et al., 2005; Jin et al., 1999; Nordberg et al., 2014). Some studies also focus on cadmium-induced CKD. One large cross-sectional study in Korea showed that elevated BCd was associated with lower eGFR in women (Hwangbo et al., 2011). Similar results were reported for the US population (Ferraro et al., 2010). Thomas et al. (2014) performed an analysis based on two large population-based, prospective

cohorts studies in Sweden. They did not find a strong association between daily dietary cadmium intake and CKD incidence. Recently, a study in China showed that the risk of CKD in subjects with a high daily dietary cadmium intake (>23.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$) was higher than in those with a low intake. Our study shows that life-time dietary cadmium is also associated with CKD in a population living in a cadmium-polluted area. The positive association in Chinese population is understandable because the exposure levels were high. Dietary cadmium-induced CKD may depend on the exposure level. Age is also related to the decline of kidney function. This effect of age was considered in our study because we calculated life-time intake and not daily intake.

Previous dietary cadmium studies mainly focused on dietary factors (Shi et al., 2018; Thomas et al., 2014). Kawata (2018) indicated that the effects of cadmium intake on CKD should be evaluated in combination with biomarkers of renal tubular damage. In addition, we speculated that the modified effects of internal cadmium levels should also be considered. Our analysis considered possible cofounders or modifiers. Our data support that CKD incidence is related to cadmium exposure, particularly in women. An association between eGFR and life-time cadmium intake was also observed in subjects with a low cadmium intake (<2.2 g) ($\beta = -0.13$, 95%CI: -5.5 to 0.01). However, the exposure levels in our study were higher than those in the two studies mentioned above, which showed values lower than 1.0 g for 60-year-old persons. Our study supports an association between life-time dietary cadmium intake and CKD at relatively high exposure levels. Therefore, additional studies are needed for general populations with low levels of exposure after considering more confounders, such as internal cadmium level and renal tubular dysfunction.

In the present study, we estimated cadmium intake mainly based on rice consumption. The reasons for this have been listed in our previous study (Jin et al., 2002). Smoking may be one source of cadmium exposure for the general population. However, the contribution of smoking to

Fig. 3. The box-plot shows the estimated glomerular filtration rate in quartile of life-time dietary cadmium intake in total population (A), male (B) and female population (C). *a*, $p < 0.01$ compared with the first quartile subgroup; *b*, $p < 0.001$ compared with the two and third quartile subgroups.

Table 2

Associations between life-time dietary cadmium intake and estimated glomerular filtration rate in multiple linear regression analysis.

	A				B			
	LCd (g)		UALB (mg/g cr)		LCd (g)		UALB (mg/g cr)	
	β	p	β	p	β	p	β	p
Model 1	-0.43 (-0.69 to -0.18)	0.001	-0.22 (-0.34 to -0.10)	< 0.01	-0.34 (-0.64 to -0.04)	0.028	-0.24 (-0.35 to -0.12)	< 0.01
Model 2	-0.43 (-0.71 to -0.16)	0.002	-0.25 (-0.38 to 0.11)	< 0.01	-0.33(-0.65 to -0.01)	0.046	-0.27(-0.40 to -0.15)	< 0.01
Model 3	-0.42 (-0.75 to -0.10)	0.01	-0.24 (-0.37 to -0.11)	< 0.01	-0.42 (-0.77 to -0.07)	0.02	-0.28 (-0.41 to -0.15)	< 0.01

Model 1: A was adjusted for baseline age, sex, and UNAG; B was additionally adjusted with BCd and UCd (B).

Model 2: Both A and B were additionally adjusted for smoking and drinking habits, BMI and follow-up hypertension.

Model 3: Both A and B were additionally adjusted for follow-up BCd, UCd, UALB and UNAG.

LCd: life-time dietary cadmium intake; UALB: urinary albumin. UALB was continuous data.

cadmium intake was lower than that of rice because the cadmium concentration in the rice was high (0.5–2.4 mg/kg). Our previous study showed that the uptake of cadmium from smoking was lower than that from rice (4.05 mg vs 22.4–545.1 mg) (Jin et al., 2002). Moreover, the amount of rice consumption is higher compared to that of other foods, such as meats and vegetables. In addition, our study shows that baseline BCd is also an independent risk factor for CKD incidence (data not shown), which is consistent with a previous study by Hwangbo et al.

(2011). In addition, our data also show that UALB is an independent risk factor for CKD incidence, which is consistent with a previous study showing that albuminuria was associated with decreased GFR (Satarug, 2018).

Our study has some advantages. First, this is a longitudinal study, which may overcome limitations in cross-sectional design. Second, we controlled for confounders, including internal cadmium exposure (BCd and UCd) and renal tubular dysfunction, because it is unclear whether

Table 3

Risk of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in relation to baseline life-time dietary cadmium intake and UALB.

	A		B			
	LCd (≥ 2.2 vs < 2.2 g)	UALB (mg/g cr)	LCd (≥ 2.2 vs < 2.2 g)	UALB (mg/g cr)		
Model 1	3.95 (1.18–13.16)	1.05 (1.01–1.08)	8.07 (1.69–37.86)	1.05 (1.02–1.09)	5.85 (1.18–28.93)	1.05 (1.02–1.08)
Model 2	6.22 (1.27–30.47)	1.06 (1.02–1.10)	31.45 (2.87–345.05)	1.09 (1.04–1.14)	18.17 (1.81–182.19)	1.08 (1.03–1.14)
Model 3	9.46 (1.61–55.53)	1.06 (1.02–1.11)	56.52 (3.51–607.78)	1.09 (1.03–1.14)	18.16 (1.75–188.85)	1.09 (1.03–1.16)

Model 1 was adjusted for baseline age, sex, and UNAG.

Model 2 was additionally adjusted for smoking and drinking habits, BMI and follow-up hypertension.

Model 3 was additionally adjusted for follow-up BCd, UCd, UALB and UNAG.

Baseline UCd (A) and both baseline BCd and UCd were also included in the models.

LCd: life-time dietary cadmium intake; UALB: urinary albumin. UALB was continuous data.

dietary cadmium is an independent risk factor for CKD. Third, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to show the association between life-time cadmium exposure and eGFR or CKD. Certainly, our study also has several limitations. The exposure levels were relatively high because our population lives in cadmium-contaminated areas. The sample size and the incidents of CKD were both relatively small. In addition, some confounders, including nutritional status, were not considered. Many subjects were lost to follow-up, which may have caused potential bias. Finally, the dietary exposure level in the present study was relatively higher than that reported in other studies. Further studies are needed to show the association between CKD and dietary exposure at low exposure levels.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, our data show that life-time dietary cadmium intake is associated with the CKD incidence in a general population living in cadmium-polluted areas. Baseline UALB is also a factor associated with follow-up CKD incidence. The risk of CKD is high for those who consume cadmium-contaminated rice. A model based on baseline UALB and life-time dietary cadmium intake may have potential in predicting CKD incidence.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Xinru Wang: Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing. **Miaomiao Wang:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing. **Wenjing Cui:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing. **Yihuai Liang:** Methodology, Data curation, Writing - review & editing. **Guoying Zhu:** Methodology, Data curation. **Taiyi Jin:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **Xiao Chen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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